

THE TWO-LEGGED ACADEMIC

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This week, I bought a new bicycle. My 8 year old e-bike with nearly 15,000 km on the odometer finally gave up the ghost, and with parts and repairs estimated at several (many several...) hundreds of euro's, I decided it was time to send it to retirement. And so the charger and battery have left the building, and I've replaced the e-bike with a fully leg-powered bike; given the 100 – 150 km per week I bike, back to 100% human power will be an adjustment, but the first few trips have been glorious.

Photo of a bicycle at the National Museum of Scotland in Edinburgh; no, this is not my bicycle, mine is a bit more mainstream. Photo © R.E. Nordquist 2025

This week also had [another reference to the Utrecht University academic as “tweebenig”](#): in English, “two-legged”, or for those of us who work with animals, “bipedal”, putting us firmly together with birds, humans, and a scant few other mammalian species, and of course a number of dinosaurs. For academics this means standing on (or cycling with) the two legs of education and research.

I consider myself proudly bipedal; I lead both research and education projects, and have both the Senior Qualification in Research and [Senior Qualification in Education](#), both of which are portfolio-based recognition of seniority. My inbox and calendar are currently filled with both education-related and research projects, and my favourite projects are combinations of both. Researching education, educating PhDs, training programs in COST actions, PhD viva examiner, love ´em all.

My university has put a lot of effort into the [Recognition and Rewards](#) program, which supports academics in broadening what is seen as a “successful” academic. When I was doing

my PhD in the early zero's, a successful academic was clearly and obviously someone who finished their PhD with more than 4 accepted publications, did a postdoc at a prestigious institution- preferably in the US, funded by a competitive funding scheme, then published in high-ranking journals, pulled in more and bigger funding, supervised a flock of PhD students who finished their PhDs with more than 4 accepted publications, went on to do postdocs at prestigious institutions.... Wash, rinse repeat. You get the idea. Fortunately, this relatively narrow view of academia has changed. This has been written about extensively, including by scholars and leaders from my own university (Kummeling et al., 2024), who stress critical role of teamwork in expertise covering research and education within the university community. This community is moving towards a broader view of academia... but we aren't there yet.

To take this outside of my immediate Utrecht context, looking at how academics at other research-intensive universities is enlightening. The membership, recognition, and belonging lens applied to interviews of associate professors in teaching-related positions at a research-intensive institution revealed (unsurprisingly) a lot of frustration and feeling lack of belonging (Snickare & Söderberg, 2026). I found the autoethnographic study on an academic career by Elda du Toit to be very relatable (du Toit, 2025), from stumbling into teaching and mentoring untrained, to finding my strengths and a more holistic approach to scholarly impact following my own seniority as an academic.

And the latter, looking at academic life as so much more than the two "pillars" of research and education, is where I find myself now. Much as I like bipedals (chickens are some of my favorite animals and vastly undervalued...), and I enjoy pedalling using my own two legs, I aspire to more. Quadrupedalism, with education, research, societal impact, and university community. Or perhaps octopedal, or millipedal: with so many ways to be and contribute to academia, two legs just doesn't feel like enough. I work to contribute to visibility and recognition of the millipedes among academics: we contribute so much to rich academic life!

Two legs will fortunately be enough to keep me bipedally bicycling on my new bicycle; life outside of work is also a critical part of academia- without time to decompress, there is no time or energy for thinking and reflecting.

du Toit, E. (2025). Teaching, research, and everything in between: An autoethnographic account of academic identity. *Review of Education*, 13(3), e70108.

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